

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

RADIO AND TELEVISION BROADCASTING IN ETHNIC MINORITY LANGUAGES IN NORTHERN VIETNAM- SOME CHARACTERISTICS AND EXPERIENCES

Nguyen Thi Minh Thu

Prof.

Faculty of Literature and Linguistic

University of Education-Thai Nguyen University Viet Nam

Thai Nguyen city, Thai Nguyen Province, Viet Nam

Abstract

The northern area is a long-standing residential area of many ethnic minorities such as Tay, Nung, Thai, Muong, Mong, Dao, Giay, Cao Lan, San Diu, Ha Nhi, Lo Lo, Kho Mu, Xinh Mun, Pu Peo ... belongs to many different language groups such as: Viet-Muong, Tay-Thai, Mong-Dao, Mon-Khmer. According to the 2009 census data, ethnic minorities account for about 62% of the total population of the Northern mountainous region. Therefore, the issue of broadcasting in ethnic minority languages in this area has important significance.

Based on the survey results on broadcasting activities of 8 languages in 7 provinces in the Northern Region, the article shows the characteristics and experiences in this work. Specific issues include: objectives, motivation, broadcasting levels of ethnic languages, structure, genre and content of ethnic language radio and television programs. Finally, analyzing and evaluating successes, limitations and proposing some solutions related to radio and television broadcasting in ethnic minority areas in Northern Vietnam.

Keywords: radio, television, ethnic minority language, the northern of Viet Nam, character and experience.

1. INTRODUCTION

Northern Vietnam is a multi-ethnic and multilingual area. According to the *List of Vietnamese Ethnic Minorities* (published by the General Statistics Office on March 21, 1979), there are about 30 ethnic groups living in the North of Vietnam, while Kinh is a majority people; the remaining ethnic groups are minorities, of which nearly 10 have written languages, and the rest have their own spoken languages and unique cultural characteristics. There is a huge gap in the populations of ethnic minorities. The survey results show that, among the ethnic minorities in Northern Vietnam, 4 ethnic groups have a population of over 1,000,000 people (Tay, Thai, Muong, Mong), 3 ethnic groups have a population of over 500,000 people (Hoa, Nung, Dao), 1 ethnic group have a population of over 100,000 people (San Chay), 3 ethnic groups have a population of over 50,000 people (Kho Mu, Giay, Phu La), 5 ethnic groups have a population of over 10,000 people (Xinh Mun, Ha Nhi, Lao, La Chi and Khang), 4 ethnic groups have a population of over 5,000 people (La Hu, La Ha, Pa Then and Lu); among the remaining ethnic groups, 6 ethnic groups have a population of over 1,000 people (Ngai, Lo Lo, Mang, Co Lao, Bo Y, Cong) and 2 ethnic groups have a population of less than 1,000 people (Si La, Pu Peo). Languages with very few users such as Xinh Mun, Ha Nhi, Lao, La Chi, Khang, La Hu, La Ha, Pa Then, Lu, Ngai, Lo Lo, Mang, Co Lao, Bo Y, Cong Pa Di, Thu Lao, and Pu Peo are considered endangered languages.

It is a fact that the distribution of ethnic groups is uneven: one ethnic group may reside in various localities and, vice versa, a locality may contain many ethnic groups living together. For example, according to the results of the 2009 census, the Mong group (1,068,189 people) was distributed mainly in 19 provinces and 745 different communes; the Dao group

(751,067 people) was distributed mainly in 23 provinces and 1035 different communes; the Tay group (1,626,392 people) was mainly distributed in 32 provinces and 2304 different communes; the Thai group (1,550,423 people) was mainly distributed in 19 provinces and 972 different communes, etc.

Such distributions brought about many drawbacks: there is a huge difference between dialects; it is difficult to develop a system of written transcript, to educate and disseminate the mother tongue of ethnic minorities; languages of small minorities are at greater risk of disappearance.

Ethnic groups in the north of Vietnam reside clearly by geographical region: some of the ethnic groups such as Thai, Tay, Kinh, and Muong live in the lowlands which are valleys and banks of rivers or streams with relatively flat terrain, fertile soil, and abundant water. Some ethnic groups such as the Kho Mu, Dao, Lao, Lu and Giay live in low mountainous areas. These ethnic groups live mainly on slopes, raising cattle and cultivating rice. The alpine area of 600m or above is the living and working space of the Mong, Xinh Mun, Ha Nhi, Cong, Si La, etc. groups. Mong people account for the greatest proportion while other ethnic groups may have a population of a few dozen to a few thousand. The mountainous terrains, hostile conditions for production and transportation, instability, along with migration practices, have created significant fluctuations in the population distribution.

With the particular characteristics of this linguistic situation, communication through radio and television in ethnic languages in Northern Vietnam has proved to play an important role in the lives of ethnic minorities, with not only advantages but also many difficulties in the process of implementation.

2. CHARACTERISTICS OF RADIO AND TELEVISION BROADCASTING

IN ETHNIC MINORITY LANGUAGES IN NORTHERN VIETNAM

2.1. Different levels of ethnic minority radio and television programs

2.1.1. National level

Currently, in Vietnam, radio and television broadcasting in ethnic minority languages is officially conducted via VOV4 channel - the Department of Ethnic Minority - the Voice of Vietnam and VTV5 program - the Television Department of Ethnic Minority - Vietnam Television Station.

The Department of Ethnic Minority VOV4 is a non-business unit directly under the Voice of Vietnam, and is the headquarter for organizing, managing, operating and producing national radio programs of the Voice of Vietnam, in order to systematically propagate the Party's guidelines and policies and the State's laws on ethnic issues reflecting the life, economy and society of ethnic minorities in a comprehensive way, contributing to preserving and promoting the cultural identity of the Vietnamese peoples. VOV4 consists of 5 permanent agencies, of which the Northern permanent office is located in Son La province, titled the Northwest Regional Agency, broadcasting in 4 languages (Mong, Dao, Thai and Tay- Nung) out of a total of 13 ethnic languages. Each language has integrated news with a duration of 30 minutes/session and 3 sessions /day.

The Television Department of Ethnic Minorities (VTV5) is a national-level television channel in ethnic minority languages (with Vietnamese subtitles) of Vietnam Television Station, mainly serving ethnic minority people in remote areas. The channel is broadcast for 24 hours a day (since 2012). The mission of the VTV5 Television Department of Ethnic Minorities is to provide information and policies of the Party and State of Vietnam, and major important events of ethnic minorities. The content of VTV5 is mainly about news, politics, and documentaries and a small proportion of entertainment. The Northern Regional Agency located in Hanoi broadcasts in 8 languages for ethnic minorities in the North (Mong, Dao, Thai, Muong, Hoa, Tay-Nung, Cao Lan, San Chi). The programs in ethnic minority languages are broadcast with a duration of 30 minutes each, including: The Mong and Dao programs are broadcast twice a day, the Thai program is broadcast 3 times a week, the Muong program is broadcast twice a week, the Hoa program is broadcast twice a month.

So in the North of Vietnam, there is communication in the languages of 8 ethnic minorities belonging to 2 central stations.

2.1.2. Provincial level

Twelve provinces (out of 35 provinces in the country) in the northern region have broadcast radio and television in nine ethnic languages. They are Yen Bai, Dien Bien, Hoa Binh, Lai Chau, Son La, Lao Cai, Ha Giang, Cao Bang, Bac Kan, Lang Son, Tuyen Quang and Thai Nguyen. The Northwestern region has 6 provinces, mainly broadcasting in Mong, Dao and Thai languages. In the Northeastern region, there are also 6 provinces where programs are broadcast in ethnic minority languages of which the main languages are Mong, Dao and Tay. Thus, in the provinces where there

are a large number of ethnic minorities, the provincial television and radio stations have made great efforts to produce ethnic language programs to meet the needs of listening, watching and updating information related to many fields in the economic, political, social life as well as entertaining, contributing to preserving languages and cultures of ethnic groups. However, the implementation of this work is different among provincial stations, there are stations which can produce multilingual programs such as Ha Giang, Lao Cai and Lai Chau, but there are also stations that can only produce programs using only a few languages like Cao Bang and Lang Son. There are languages that are broadcast in many stations such as Mong, Dao, Thai but there are languages that are only broadcast in one station such as Giay and Ha Nhi. Most of the stations have broadcast both television and radio programs in the above languages, but there are also languages that are only broadcast on radio or television such as Giay on Lao Cai radio station, and Tay on Thai Nguyen radio station and Tay on Tuyen Quang and Ha Giang television station.

In the North of Vietnam, district-level radio and television stations do not produce ethnic language television programs due to management regulations for ethnic language television programs. The production of radio programs is also very limited, currently only Tan Son District Radio Station, Phu Tho Province produces a program in Muong language.

2.2. Frequency, duration, and time frame of ethnic minority radio and television programs in Northern Vietnam

2.2.1. National level

The broadcasting of programs in 3 languages: Mong, Dao and Thai at the Northwestern Agency of the Voice of Vietnam has a total duration of 375 minutes/day. The duration of each program is 30 minutes and it is broadcast 3 times a day. In the morning, from 5.00 to 5.30, Mong program is aired, followed by Thai program from 5.30 to 6.00, from 7.00 to 7.30, Dao program is broadcast, and finally from 8.00 to 8.30, Tay- Nung program is broadcast. These programs are re-broadcast at 11.00 in the same order: Dao program (11.00 – 11.30), Thai program (11.30 – 12.00), Mong program (12.00 – 12.30), Tay- Nung program (12.00 – 12.30) and (16.00-16.30). In the evening, Mong program is aired at 19.30, Thai program at 20.00, Dao program at 20.30. From 18.45 to 19.00, a 15-minute program of music with one language per day.

The duration of new products per day 55 minutes (including a 30-minute program, while replaying a 10-minute newsletter, a 15-minute music program).

The Television Department of Ethnic Minorities (VTV5) - Vietnam Television Station has the main broadcast time in the morning (5:30, 6:00, 7:00) and early afternoon (from 13:30 to 15:30), the broadcast duration is 30 minutes per program with the total duration of 180 minutes/day. The Mong and Dao programs are broadcast regularly and stably, while the Tay, Thai, Cao Lan, San Chi and Muong programs are broadcast in turn.

For example, this is the list of programs in ethnic minority language broadcast on September 15, 2019 (Sunday): 13.30: Mong program, 14.00: Dao program,

14.30: Cao Lan program. The programs on 16, 17, 18 September 2019 (Monday) had a time frame as follows: 5.30: Mong program, 6.00: Dao program, 7.00: San Chi; 13.30: Mong program, 14.00: Dao program, 14.30: Thai program. On September 19, 2019, the Tay program was broadcast at 7.00 in the morning, the Cao Lan program was broadcast at 14.30. On September 20, 2019, the Cao Lan program was broadcast at 7 and the Muong program was broadcast at 14.30.

2.2.2. Provincial level

Each radio and television station has different time frames, but the average broadcast duration of each ethnic language program is from 15 to 30 minutes/program. For example, Hoa Binh station has a news program in Muong language on HBTB, and this news program is broadcast on the frequency of FM 96.3 MHz. Son La station has television programs in Mong and Thai languages on STV channel; Each language has 3 programs (a news program with the duration of 15 minutes/session, a magazine program with the duration of 30 minutes/session, a program about the changes of rural areas is broadcast with the duration of 10 minutes/session.). In addition, Son La station also broadcasts in Mong and Thai language on the frequency of FM 96 MHz, there are 2 programs in each language: a general news program and a music program, each program has a broadcast duration of 30 minutes/session. Lao Cai station has programs in Mong and Dao languages on THLC channel; each language has 4 programs: news, music, ethnic minority reality and development. Broadcast duration is 15 minutes/session. Ha Giang has programs in Mong, Dao and Tay languages on HGTV channel, each language has two programs: a general news program, an ethnic minority cultural and arts program. Broadcast duration is 30 minutes/session. In addition, Ha Giang also uses languages such as the Mong, Dao, and Tay in the general news radio program and the music radio program, each of which has a duration of 30 minutes/session on the frequency of FM 100 MHz. Cao Bang province has Mong and Dao languages on CBTB channel with the duration of 30 minutes/session. In addition, Cao Bang also uses Mong, Dao and Tay-Nung languages in radio program. Each language is broadcast in 2 programs: news program and general arts program. The broadcast duration is 30 minutes/session on 99 MHz FM frequency.

2.3. Topics and contents of ethnic minority radio and television programs in Northern Vietnam

2.3.1. Topics and contents at national level

In general, all programs have diverse categories and contents, which reflects issues in the lives of Vietnamese peoples in general and ethnic minority peoples in particular in a comprehensive way.

On VTV5, the Mong program has the following categories: Science and technology for production and life, Exploring ethnic cultures, Good people with good actions, Sunday music, Northwestern news, Studying about policy and law, Health and life, What farmers need to know, Building the Party, Traffic safety is everyone's happiness, Knowledge and life, Mong ethnic culture, Clean water and sanitation for village environment.

The three programs produced at the Northwestern agency have a total of 14 categories which are alternatively broadcast (Monday: Building the Party - Ethnic minorities with the National Assembly; Tuesday: What farmers need to know - Science and Technology for life; Wednesday: Health and life; Thursday: Good people with good actions; Friday: Studying about policy and law; Saturday: Learning about the beauty of ethnic cultures - Weekly art (Weekend tour - Radio Stories - Fairy Tales - Comedy); Sunday: Music on demand.)

In addition to the current affairs and politics, there is a large amount of news and articles on the unique cultural beauty of the Northwest ethnic groups, promoting the preservation and promotion of cultural values. Some typical subjects are as follows: *Ethnic minorities with National Assembly*; *Science and Technology for production and life*; and *Studying about policy and law*. Annually, it is directly reported on *Hoa ban Festival*, *Tam giac mach Festival*, *Then folk song and Tinh Festival*, and additional activities to honor, preserve and promote various forms of cultural heritages of the provinces such as Dien Bien, Ha Giang, Cao Bang, etc.; associating cultural preservation with promoting potentials of tourism strengths, socio-economic development of localities.

The results showed that the contents currently being broadcast in ethnic languages on the national and local channels were welcomed and adored by the local people at a high rate. In particular, people are especially interested in issues such as news of the country and locality, and cultural and artistic programs. The contents related to agricultural techniques, health and life skills are necessary and suitable for only some groups of audience (farmers, young adults, older adults), so the rate is lower. The content related to policies and laws received lower interest than the others, possibly because it is not performed in a lively and appealing way.

2.3.2. Topics and contents at local level

In general, local radio and television programs have focused on outstanding national and local issues (including politics, economics, and culture), appropriate to natural, economic, living and cultural conditions of ethnic minorities, and mentioned issues that are specific to each region. However, the percentage of topics and contents varies among the provincial stations.

For example, in the Tay-Nung television program of provincial stations, the main content is information on all aspects of the locality. Lang Son and Bac Kan television stations have an additional cultural show/program. In other stations, the dissemination of knowledge and information about policies and laws has not been paid much attention. This type of information and news about the country, enrichment experience and life skills can be shown in different articles.

Looking at the survey results of the contents of television programs in Thai language at Yen Bai, Son La and Dien Bien stations, it can be seen that contents related to social life (including education, health, transportation, public healthcare, environment, disease prevention, social evils, etc.) account for a higher proportion than other fields (economic, political and cultural issues).

Looking at the survey results of the contents of television programs in Tuyen Quang, Ha Giang and Bac Can, it can be found that information on cultural topics is quite limited. Economic and political news accounts for a larger proportion while there is a shortage of information on security and defense.

Especially, in some provincial stations, there are programs of which contents reflect a major issue, a typical phenomenon of a locality or a community. Those programs are well received by people because they are very close and practical. For example, on November 1, 2017, Son La radio and television station reported on the issue: *Finding the solution to the helmet problem for Thai women*. This reportage mentioned a real difficulty of Thai women when wearing helmets in accordance with the law because Thai women have a tradition of wearing high bun (*tang cau*) if they are maidens.

2.4. Forms of radio and television programs in ethnic minority languages in Northern Vietnam

2.4.1. Layout, texture, category

In general, the layout and texture of ethnic minority radio and television programs have not been paid much attention. Programs are usually organized according to a fixed formula. For example, the general news program always follows this pattern: Introductory music, Greetings and inviting the audience to watch the program, introducing news in the program (the Mong program in Thai Nguyen and Ha Giang) or instead of invitation to watch the program, the news are shown one by one (the Mong program on Lao Cai radio). There are not many interesting comments, marking the styles of the editors and reporters.

Categories are not diverse, and news and reportage account for a large proportion. There is almost no news in which reporters work on the spot. However, the Thai language program in the Northwestern stations does have the interview category. Interviews are not only carried out in the form of reports, but also in the form of long interviews or so-called seminars. With this form, the audience receives information directly from the interviewees who are usually knowledgeable about a certain field or experts. This form creates a more effective and efficient way for the people to receive information.

Categories with higher levels of thinking, intelligence and reasoning such as the political press (with items such as *editorials, commentary, investigation, criticism*) or those are vivid, profound, soft and attractive as *press skits and stories* of the *political-art press* have not been produced by ethnic language radio and television channels in the North.

2.4.2. Visual and audio features

This is a feature and advantage of television over other types and media of communication. In general, television programs in ethnic minority languages in Northern provinces have tried to use a vivid and accurate audio and visual system suitable to the content of the programs.

However, there are still many television programs using inappropriate images, lacking graphics, using uninteresting comments, and not having various sounds. In particular, most of the live audio (or the conversations between interviewers and interviewees in news

stories and reports) is in Kinh (Vietnamese) language, so the reporters have to translate it into ethnic languages and do the voiceover, which partly affects the interest of ethnic peoples.

2.5. Dialect issues in radio and television programs in ethnic minority languages

This is one of the important factors affecting the effectiveness and efficiency of radio and television programs and leads to many practical problems in use.

Currently, on the Voice of Vietnam Radio, the languages selected for broadcast are the most populous languages with a large number of users from many ethnic groups (often referred to as regional common language), with status and reputation of social culture and official writing system, etc. However, the issue of selecting dialects is still debatable.

With regards to the Mong radio program, during the period when it was broadcast in Hanoi (from 1991 to 2008), the chosen dialect was the Hoa Mong dialect of Sapa in Lao Cai province and Mu Cang Chai in Yen Bai Province. This choice is reasonable because within 5 Mong branches, Flowery Mong, Red Mong, Blue Mong share the same Flowery Mong dialect, making up the majority of the Mong people. This dialect is also the dialect with the most abundant vocabulary. In terms of accent, this dialect has a moderate accent which is neither too heavy nor too light. It is considered the standard dialect because it has a system of 58 consonants, 11 vowels, 24 rhymes and 8 tones of the Mong phonetic system. The Mong of other Mong branches can hear and understand the Flowery Mong dialect. The Hoa Mong dialect of Sa Pa (Lao Cai) and Mu Cang Chai (Yen Bai) is also the dialect chosen by the Ministry of Education as the basis for building the Vietnamese Mong script.

However, since 2008 when Mong programs started to be produced in Northwestern Station, Trang Mong dialect in Long He commune, Thuan Chau district, Son La province has been selected. This is a regional dialect which is not only poor in lexical resource, but also lacks 4 rhymes, 5 vowels and 2 tones in the Mong phonetic system.

The Thai language program currently uses the Thai Son La script, which already has Thai word processing software. The dialects used are Black Thai in Thuan Chau, Muong La, Mai Son (Son La) and Thai in Dien Bien. With these dialects, most Black Thai and White Thai in the Northwestern provinces can hear and understand. However, Thai people in Nghe An and Thanh Hoa consider it hard to hear and understand.

In the national television station (VTV5 channel), most of the ethnic minority television programs are produced by local stations. The editors and reporters are mostly seconded officials from different localities who are replaced every 3-5 years, so they just use their own dialects instead of conducting research to find out which dialects should be used.

The survey results also show that in the provincial radio and television stations in the northern region of Vietnam, the selection of which regional dialects to use in the programs has also been paid attention by some stations based on the certain criteria such as whether it is a dialect with a large population of people or a dialect

with a relatively complete phonetic system. For example: The Red Dao dialect is used in the Dao language program produced by the Lao Cai Television and Broadcasting Station because there are many Đơ Dao people in these localities. Lai Chau Television and Broadcasting Station use the Dao Khau dialect because there are many Dao Khau ethnic people living there. Some local stations, such as Dien Bien Television and Broadcasting Station, still use both Đen Thai and Trang Thai. In one program, there are two reporters, one using Trang Thai and one using Đen Thai. Most of the radio stations use dialects of the editors and reporters who are working in there.

3. EXPERIENCES OF THE RADIO AND TELEVISION WORK IN ETHNIC MINORITY LANGUAGE IN NORTHERN VIETNAM

3.1. The strengths

The content of radio and television programs at the national and local levels is diverse and plentiful, not only serving the propaganda of the Party's directions and policies and the laws of the State but also meeting the needs to update current information on the situation of the country and the locality, information directly related to the economic, cultural and recreational life of ethnic minorities.

The frequency, time frame, and broadcast time have been quite stable and ensured; priority has been given to the time frame suitable for the working and living conditions of ethnic minority peoples.

3.2. The limitations

The production of radio and television programs in ethnic language in many stations at both national and local levels has not been proactive because some stations rely heavily on the provincial station or programs in Kinh (Vietnamese) language. Most ethnic language radio and television programs are use and translate from news in Kinh (Vietnamese) language programs, so the content is duplicated to a certain extent.

Human resources for ethnic minority radio and television broadcasting are inadequate in quantity, and limited in professional qualifications (with regards to ethnic languages, translating, editing and program making techniques).

The distribution of content is not really balanced, there is a shortage of cultural and artistic contents, and information to warn people against social evils (vices, crimes, environmental issues, etc.).

The selection of languages and dialects for radio and television programs is not really appropriate.

The form (layout, texture, and audio and visual features) of radio and television programs in ethnic minority languages is not very lively, attractive and suitable. The broadcast time is limited.

4. CONCLUSION

Radio and television are the two most popular forms of communication, which are most concerned and watched/listened to by ethnic minorities in the North in particular, and in Vietnam in general. Radio and television programs in ethnic languages have shown an important role in the regular transmission of information, maintaining the pride and awareness of preserving ethnic minority languages for a large number of communities living in the Northern region. Radio and television in ethnic languages in the North have achieved remarkable results in the number of languages broadcasted and televised, program content, frequency and duration of radio and television programs. However, broadcasting in ethnic languages in Northern Vietnam is facing many difficulties, the effectiveness is not very high, and the level of attractiveness is not high. It is important to find solutions to improve the quality and efficiency of this activity in the North of Vietnam.

References

1. Tran Tri Doi (2016), Languages of ethnic minorities in Vietnam, Hanoi National University Publishing House, Hanoi.
2. Nguyen Thanh Giang (2016), Production of radio programs in ethnic minority languages in Ha Giang Radio and Television Station, Master thesis, Academy of Journalism and Communication, Hanoi.
3. Khuong Thi Nguyet (2018), Managing the television program in Thai language at Northwestern Radio and Television Station, Master Thesis, Academy of Journalism and Communication, Hanoi.
4. Many authors (2018), Communication in ethnic minority languages in Northern Vietnam, Proceedings of National Scientific Conference, Thai Nguyen.
5. Nguyen Thi Le Thuy (2013), Improving the quality of radio programs in ethnic minority languages in the northern mountain provinces, Master Thesis, Academy of Journalism and Communication, Hanoi.
6. Institute of Linguistics (2002), Situation and language policies in Vietnam, Social Sciences Publishing House, Hanoi.